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**Teachers Perception of Teaching Aided Computer Tablet for
Preschool Children on Online Learning**

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: July 6, 2022 Revised: July 12, 2022 Accepted: August 17, 2022 Published: Sep 01, 2022</p>	<p>This article describes about Kuantan teachers' level of knowledge in using tablets for teaching and learning. The use of technology in teacher teaching is becoming more widespread and growing in the field of education. Similarly with computer tablet technology, its use is now also expanded into the field of education. Computer tablets are becoming an option for use as teaching aid in education. The computer tablet factor of choice is because it can meet students 'interests and needs increase students' attention to lessons and provide an effective teaching environment for teachers (Gündüz, 2010; Aksal, 2011; Delen & Bulut, 2011; Güzel, 2011). Computer tablet in contemporary education offers also potential to provide creative and communicative activities for children (Kim, 2020). Although there are many benefits in teaching and learning, the use of computers is still not widely practiced by teachers. The respondents consisted of 110 randomly selected preschool teachers in Kuantan. Data was collected through questionnaires. The descriptive method is used to analyze data to obtain frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation. The findings were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 26.0. The findings show that overall teacher has good knowledge of the use of computer tablets and has a positive perception of the importance of teaching using computer tablet as teaching. Hence, the teachers involved had a positive perception of computer tablet-assisted in teaching and learning as an educational innovation. The high trust and confidence of teachers in the use of computers tablet in teaching as support for the implementation of computer technology in education.</p>
<p>Keywords: Teacher Perception Computer tablet Preschool Online Learning</p> <p></p>	

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INTRODUCTION

The use of technology has a huge influence on each of its users. Human methods of learning have changed in tandem and in parallel with developments in the field of technology (Naismith et al., 2004). Technology can respond to the needs of individuals in daily life. The rapid development of information technology today has changed teaching methods to suit the current needs of students (Aris, 2007). Technology contributes to enrichment in learning when used in teaching and learning environments for teachers and students. At the same time, teachers can create an effective learning environment with the support of technology (Turan, 2010). The teacher teaching environment should be supported with Internet technology as well (Batvi, 2012) so that teachers can integrate technology into their teaching. The use of technology in teaching opens up opportunities for national education to move to a more modern and dynamic learning pattern during the covid-19 pandemic. Martin et al., (2019) also stated that online learning also has advantages such as being able to minimize time and effort so that the minimized energy can be used to perform other activities outside of lesson time. Technology is causing a change in the way teachers teach and students learn from the use of stone tablets to the use of computer tablets (Yusup, 2015). Mobile learning is defined as learning that occurs without being limited by fixed location and learning that utilizes mobile technology (Sharples, 2000).

One of the technological innovations in education today is the computer tablet. The computer tablet is a technological device that has become a phenomenon and is very popular in all parts of the world because its use allows mobile learning to be created making students able to learn flexibly that is no matter where and used at any time, regardless of time. even not limited to just in the classroom (Stewart, 2013). Computer tablets are seen to have the potential to be a useful teaching aid because they are very intuitive, portable, and the touch features available on computer tablets make the device easy to use by all ages, especially children. With the advancement of mobile technology, teachers are more interested in using mobile devices to support teaching and facilitation activities (Frohberg, Göth, & Schwabe, 2009). Therefore, this study focuses on teachers' perception of teaching aided computer tablets for preschool children on online learning in Kuantan, Pahang.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Many teachers, especially early childhood education teachers feel unprepared and feel unable to integrate technology into their teaching (Wood et al., 2008). That statement is supported in the study Beschorner & Hutchison, (2013) which stated inexperienced teachers could not use a computer tablet under any circumstances. . In addition, the results of the study indicate that computer tablets, or tablets, can be used in a variety of ways as teaching tools to support the early literacy teaching of children (Beschorner & Hutchison 2013).

Clark and Abbott (2016) looked at how computer tablets impact learning in literacy, numeracy and learning skills. Mobile technology is more motivating and more fun than the tools used in traditional classrooms. Computer tablets, in particular, can be used anywhere anytime and promote individual learning, just as teachers can use the tool as a tool for student self-learning (Lemke, Coughlin, & Reifsneider, 2009). The use of computer tablets does not seem to affect the overall learning or learning performance of students (Sundvik et al., 2016). The focus should be on the integration of technology with various groups of children, followed by an increase in the number of teachers who are less exposed to the use of computer tablets, or use tablets that have more specific uses or other forms of technology for literacy learning.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

1. What is the level of teacher's knowledge using computer tablet as teaching aid in learning?
2. What is the teachers' perception on the importance of computer tablet-assisted teaching to preschool children?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Touch screen technology has changed the way children interact with gadgets or technological devices. More interactive and fast learning can be realized with the convenience of touch screen technology such as computer tablets. The use of computer tablets is more convenient than traditional computers because in terms of size, display interactivity, use of applications and easier to carry anywhere makes the computer tablet as a very popular device and the main choice of teachers as the use of teaching aid (Stewart, 2013). Over time, the development of technology, especially computer tablet technology, facilitates the daily affairs of human life, including teachers managing teaching documents and especially teaching aids. The Malaysia Education Development Plan (PPPM) 2013-2025 in line with the seventh shift in the transformation of the education system to utilize ICT (Pelan Pembangunan Pendidikan Malaysia, 2013). Thus, the use of teaching aid based on electronic materials such as computer tablets is seen as very efficient and suitable for use in preschool for all subjects. The advancement of the use of electronic media in learning can create a learning environment in schools that is more sophisticated, futuristic and in line with the changes of the information technology era.

Computer tablet-assisted teaching attracts children's feelings of love and interest to focus on the learning process. The result of Blackwell's research (2014), shows more active student involvement in learning that involves technology compared to teaching that simply uses tools in traditional classrooms. Furthermore, computer tablet-assisted teaching is able to help teachers diversify their teaching materials through access to various interesting applications on computer tablets to engage children in learning sessions (Stewart, 2013), at the same time helping teachers achieve teaching objectives. The advantage of a computer tablet is that allows it to be used everywhere and at any time and can encourage individual learning, such as using a computer tablet as a tool to improve the concept of 'scaffolding' for children (Lemke, Coughlin, & Reifsneider, 2009).

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted by using a quantitative research method as an approach and using questionnaire techniques to obtain information on teachers' perception of teaching aided computer tablets for preschool children on online learning during the covid-19 pandemic. Questionnaires are the easiest and most successful way to obtain standard data from a large and comprehensive sample size (Babbie, 2001; Gay et al., 2012). A total of 110 preschool teachers were selected as respondents in this study. Random sampling was used for the survey design of this study. According to Jamilah Mohd Basir (2012), random sampling is easy to use because of cost and time factors and even getting a sample that is truly representative of the population in a place is difficult and difficult to do.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

The research question is what is the level of teacher's knowledge using computer tablet as teaching aid in learning. Analysis using descriptive statistical methods is shown through the study data in the table below. The researcher uses the mean score interpretation used by Alias (1999) as follows:

Table 1: Mean Score Interpretation Scale

Mean Score	Interpretation of Min Score
1.00-1.80	Very Low
1.81-2.60	Low
2.61-3.40	Average
3.41-4.20	High
4.21-5.00	Very High

Source: Alias, B. (1999)

According to studies conducted by James T Croasmun & Lee Ostrom (2011), there is a high consistency of Cronbach alpha values when done to large population size groups employing statements (SD) Strongly Disagree, (D) Disagree, (U) Uncertain, (A) Agree, and (SA) Strongly Agree.

Table 2: Teacher's Knowledge Using Computer tablet as Teaching Aid in Learning

No.	Knowledge Items Teachers Use Computers Tablet as teaching aids in learning	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Uncertain	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean
1.	Computer tablet-assisted teaching facilitates learning sessions.	1 (0.9%)	6 (5.5%)	36 (32.7%)	52 (47.3%)	15 (13.6%)	3.67
2.	Teachers need courses on computer tablet -assisted teaching.	0 (0.0%)	11 (10.0%)	20 (18.2%)	53 (48.2%)	26 (23.6%)	3.85
3.	Teachers are sure computer tablet-assisted teaching helps in learning sessions.	0 (0.0%)	8 (7.3%)	42 (38.2%)	48 (43.6%)	12 (10.9%)	3.58
4.	Disclosure on how to handle computer tablet-assisted teaching is especially necessary for teachers.	0 (0.0%)	7 (6.4%)	29 (26.4%)	54 (49.1%)	20 (18.2%)	3.79
5.	Computer tablet-assisted teaching skills help in the learning process.	3 (2.7%)	9 (8.2%)	27 (24.5%)	51 (46.4%)	20 (18.2%)	3.69
6.	Teachers will provide various uses of educational 'apps' contained in computers tablet.	1 (0.9%)	5 (4.5%)	29 (26.4%)	63 (57.3%)	12 (10.9%)	3.73
7.	If given the opportunity, teachers are interested in further learning the teaching skills of a computer tablet.	1 (0.9%)	4 (3.6%)	23 (20.9%)	55 (50.0%)	27 (24.5%)	3.94
8.	Attending tablet computer-aided teaching courses helps teachers in improving proficiency using computers tablet.	0 (0.0%)	5 (4.5%)	24 (21.8%)	54 (49.1%)	27 (24.5%)	3.94
9.	Computer tablet-assisted teaching can boost teacher skills.	2 (1.8%)	5 (4.5%)	26 (23.6%)	55 (50.0%)	22 (20.0%)	3.82
10.	Teachers are constantly diversifying teaching methods that help computers tablet.	0 (0.0%)	5 (4.5%)	28 (25.5%)	62 (56.4%)	15 (13.6%)	3.79

Table 2 shows that each item of knowledge of teachers using computer tablet as teaching aid in learning is at a high level. All 10 items showed a high mean. A total of two items that have the same mean value and the highest that if given the opportunity, teachers are interested in learning more computer tablet -assisted teaching skills ($M = 3.94$ and $SP = 0.827$) and items attending computer tablet -assisted teaching courses help teachers in improving skills in using computer tablet ($M = 3.94$ and $SP = 0.805$). In terms of frequency and percentage of items if given the opportunity, teachers interested in further learning the teaching skills of a computer tablet showed that a total of 55 teachers (50.0%) agreed and a total of 27 teachers (24.5%) strongly agreed, then a total of 23 teachers (20.9%) uncertain, a total of 4 teachers (3.6%) disagree and for this item only one teacher (0.9%) strongly disagree. In terms of frequency and percentage of items attending computer tablet -assisted teaching courses help teachers in improving skills in using computer tablets. showed that a total of 54 teachers (49.1%) agreed and a total of 27 teachers (24.5%) strongly agreed, then a total of 24 teachers (21.8%) uncertain, while a total of 5 teachers (4.5%) disagree and for this item none of the teachers (0.0%) strongly disagree. While for the item with the lowest mean is that the teacher are sure the computer tablet -assisted teaching helps in the learning session with $Mean = 3.58$ and $SP = 0.783$. In terms of frequency and percentage, a total of 48 teachers (43.6%) agreed, a total of 42 teachers (38.2%) uncertain, a total of 12 teachers (10.9%) strongly agreed, a total of 8 teachers (7.3%) stated disagree and none of the teachers (0.0%) strongly disagree. Overall, it shows that teachers' knowledge of using computer tablets as teaching aid in learning is high (mean = 3.780).

Table 3: Teachers' Perception on The Importance of Computer Tablet-Assisted Teaching to Preschool Children

No.	Teacher's View Item on the Importance of Computer Tablet-Assisted Teaching to Children	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Uncertain	Agree	Strongly Agree	Mean
1.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching raises children's interest in learning process.	3 (2.7%)	2 (1.8%)	28 (25.5%)	59 (53.6%)	18 (16.4%)	3.79
2.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching can boost children's creativity.	0 (0.0%)	7 (6.4%)	44 (40.0%)	49 (44.5%)	10 (9.1%)	3.56
3.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching makes children more active in learning.	1 (9.0%)	6 (5.5%)	48 (43.6%)	43 (39.1%)	12 (10.9%)	3.54
4.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching in the learning process can improve children's literacy mastery in lessons.	3 (2.7%)	11 (10.0%)	35 (31.8%)	47 (42.7%)	14 (12.7%)	3.53
5.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching can create a fun learning atmosphere for children.	0 (0.0%)	8 (7.3%)	30 (27.3%)	55 (50.0%)	17 (15.5%)	3.74
6.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching can motivate children to learn.	0 (0.0%)	17 (15.5%)	41 (37.3%)	43 (39.1%)	9 (8.2%)	3.40
7.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching can improve children's imagination.	0 (0.0%)	17 (15.5%)	41 (37.3%)	42 (38.2%)	10 (9.1%)	3.41
8.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching can help children to improve their achievement.	2 (1.8%)	16 (14.5%)	37 (33.6%)	49 (44.5%)	6 (5.5%)	3.37
9.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching can help children in solving a task.	1 (0.9%)	16 (14.5%)	43 (39.1%)	44 (40.0%)	6 (5.5%)	3.35
10.	Computer Tablet-assisted teaching can improve children's communication.	8 (7.3%)	31 (28.2%)	34 (30.9%)	32 (29.1%)	5 (4.5%)	2.95

Table 3 shows that the items in the frequency of teachers' perception on the importance of computer tablet-assisted teaching to children are at high, medium and low levels. There is one item that indicates the mean is at a low level, four items that have a medium mean and the rest are high. The item with the highest mean is computer tablet-assisted teaching raises children's interest in the learning process (M= 3.79 and SP= 0.836). In terms of frequency and percentage, 59 teachers (53.6%) agree, a total of 28 (25.5%) who were uncertain whether computer tablet-assisted teaching could increase children's interest in the learning process or not. Only 2 teachers (1.8%) said they disagree that computer tablet-assisted teaching increased children's interest in learning. While the lowest mean was computer tablet-assisted teaching could improve children's communication (M= 2.95 and SP= 1.026). In terms of frequency and percentage, 34 teachers (30.9%) uncertain, 32 people (29.1%) agree, 31 (28.2%) disagree, 8 (7.3%) strongly disagree and only 5 teachers (4.5%) strongly agree. However, the number of teachers said they agreed that computer tablets improve children's communication is more than the number of teachers who disagree. Overall, the frequency of the teacher's view of the importance of computer tablet-assisted teaching to children is at a moderate level (mean = 3.464) and the teacher has a rather positive view of the importance of computer tablet-assisted teaching.

DISCUSSIONS

Teachers' Perception from Aspect of Knowledge

The findings of this study show teacher's knowledge that computer tablet-assisted teaching skills help in the learning process. Overall the teacher's knowledge of using a computer tablet in teaching is high in contrast to studies by Long, Liang, & Yu (2013) state in China, nearly half of teachers do not know how to apply computer tablets to their teaching and learning and lack the confidence to understand the directions contained in computer tablets. The findings show the majority of teachers agree that they need a course on computer tablet-assisted teaching and are in line with the study Furman et al., (2019) which shows teachers need teaching to use the latest technology facilities so that their full potential can be achieved by teachers and as a support material in teacher teaching. Next, based on the findings of the study, teachers support constantly diversifying teaching methods that help with computer tablets. These findings are consistent with studies Otterborn et al., (2020) which found teachers are diversifying various ways of using computer tablets to support literacy teaching to preschoolers. There are some teachers expressing doubts about the use of computer tablets in learning. Teachers who lack knowledge about the functions of the computer tablet itself will have a feeling of hesitation to use the computer tablet in learning.

Teachers' Perception on The Importance of Computer Tablet-Assisted Teaching to Preschool Children

The results of this study found that many teachers most agree that the importance of computer tablet-assisted teaching increases children's interest in the learning process and it coincides with the study Fridberg et al.,

(2018) agree that simple equipment in learning can stimulate students' interest in Science subjects. In addition, this study shows that the importance of computer tablet-assisted teaching makes children more active in learning and the importance of computers tablet makes children actively supported by the results of the study McKenna (2012) who have examined the usefulness of computers tablet in learner learning which shows that increased student motivation to learn makes learners more active in computer tablet-aided teaching and coincides with the results of studies Blackwell (2014) which found that student engagement is more active in learning that involves technology than in teaching that only uses tools in traditional classrooms. This study also shows that teachers agree that computer tablet-assisted teaching can improve children's creativity and this finding is in line with the findings of studies conducted by Chen & Sager (2011). The findings showed that the diversity of functions on computers tablet helps improve children's technology skills to help improve students' creativity. In addition, the findings found that the number of teachers agreeing importance of computer-assisted teaching can motivate children to learn is more than teachers who disagree and are also supported by the results of the study. Flewitt, Messer, & Kucirkova (2014) which found that the use of ICT in literacy activities stimulated children's motivation and focus in learning. In fact, these findings are also supported by Enriquez (2010) that the use of computers tablet increases motivation and at the same time gives a positive impression on learning outcomes. This can also be supported by Roschelle et al. (2010) that the use of computer-based technology becomes a good simulation and motivation for children.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

From the analysis of the data, it was found that overall teachers involved had a positive perception of computer tablet-aided teaching in learning as an educational innovation. Teachers' high trust and confidence in the use of computers tablet in teaching as their support for the implementation of computer technology in education. The task of the teacher plays a very important role in achieving the established learning objectives. This relates to the effective method of learning chosen by the teacher as a teaching aid to help the learning process. Computer tablet-assisted teaching is one of the effective methods of facilitating children's understanding and skills. As evidenced from the results of the study, many teachers in Kuantan agree that computer tablet-assisted teaching to children is important to help attract their focus to learning and create a fun learning environment for children. Therefore, teachers should explore and prepare themselves with the latest technical knowledge to move in line with advances in education.

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